

Clinical Insights into Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs

Shaik Khadeer Ahamed^{1*}, Ramgondola Vijaya Laxmi², Rohith Kumar A², Mettu Nandu Kumar²,
Vishal Chakala², Rama Rao Tadikonda³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharm D, CMR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

²Pharm D students, CMR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

³Principal, Department of Pharmaceutical chemistry, CMR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

ABSTRACT: Medications with a narrow therapeutic index (NTI), such as phenytoin, warfarin, and vancomycin, require precise dosing to avoid adverse effects and ensure they remain effective. This is particularly important for at-risk groups like elderly individuals or those with multiple health conditions. The therapeutic index (TI) is a key measurement that indicates the range between a drug's therapeutic and toxic levels. NTI drugs need careful management because even small changes in their concentration can lead to significant risks and impact their therapeutic benefits. Factors unique to each patient, such as age, existing health conditions, and genetic differences, can affect how NTI drugs are metabolized and their overall effectiveness. As a result, therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) is crucial for tailoring dosing strategies and minimizing the risk of harm. Interactions between NTI drugs and other medications, especially those that involve cytochrome P450 enzymes, can influence drug concentrations, making treatment more complex. The growing field of personalized medicine, which includes pharmacogenomics, aims to improve outcomes by customizing drug therapies based on individual genetic characteristics. Proper management of NTI drugs requires teamwork among healthcare professionals, including doctors, pharmacists, and nurses. Continued research, along with advancements in drug delivery systems and artificial intelligence, holds potential to enhance the safety and effectiveness of NTI medications.

KEYWORDS: Carbamazepine, NTI drugs, Therapeutic index, Phenytoin, Vancomycin, Warfarin, Heparin.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, there is no clear agreement on the definition of a Narrow Therapeutic Index medication or its properties. Narrow therapeutic window, narrow therapeutic range, narrow therapeutic ratio, and narrow therapeutic index (NTI) are some of the words that have been used interchangeably. These medications have also been called difficult drugs, difficulty drugs, critical bioavailability drugs, critical dose drugs, critical usage drugs, and complicated pharmaceuticals (1). Even if there isn't a single, widely recognized definition of NTI medications, in 1990 narrow therapeutic index (NTI) drugs are defined by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) as "those drugs where small differences in dose or blood concentration may lead to serious therapeutic failures and/or adverse drug reactions that are life-threatening or result in persistent or significant disability or incapacity" (2). To ensure the safety and benefit of NTI medications, highly customized dosage, as well as careful patient monitoring and evaluation, are necessary. Many reasons can make it difficult to keep patients within the therapeutic range, or "window," and these factors all contribute to the unpredictability in the pharmacodynamics of NTI medications.

These elements fall into three broad categories: The condition of the patient's illness, the method of treatment that goes along with a particular treatment (such as education and observation), and the medication itself (3).

Drugs' high toxicity and lack of effectiveness can be caused by a variety of factors, including the following five: the appropriate drug, dosage, timing, duration, and age (4). Since the ideal dosage for each patient varies, the potential risk associated with the majority of NTI medications is increased. When two patients receive the same dosage of an NTI medication, the outcome can be very different. Elderly patients frequently have comorbid diseases that may impact their response to therapy, and their age might have an impact on a drug's pharmacodynamics (5,6).

NTI medications have a tight range of dosages needed to provide the intended effect; supra-range doses cause severe side effects, while sub-range doses can result in dangerous treatment failures. These pharmacodynamic reactions that carry the risk of adverse patient safety events are particularly pertinent to vulnerable populations, including elderly patients, patients with comorbid conditions, and patients who are taking several medications (7). Because of the limited range of safe uses for these medications, it is essential to

constantly monitor patients when they start and continue using an NTI medication. When starting NTI treatments like digoxin, tacrolimus, or phenytoin, practitioners frequently reiterate the adage "start low and go slow." Furthermore, several studies have demonstrated that tracking NTI medication levels for various therapeutic classes can guarantee proper therapeutic dosage and improve patient safety results (8).

PHARMACOLOGICAL BASIS OF NTI DRUGS THERAPEUTIC INDEX CONCEPT

Therapeutic index (TI), sometimes referred to as the therapeutic ratio, contrasts the blood concentration at which a medication has a therapeutic effect with the quantity that is poisonous (in human research) or causes death (in animal studies). The range of dosages at which a drug seems to work in clinical trials for a median of participants without incurable side effects is known as the therapeutic index (TI) in clinical practice (9).

A drug's therapeutic index (TI), which can be computed using different pairs of pharmacological and toxicological end points, is a quantifiable link between its efficacy (pharmacology) and safety (toxicology) (10).

Due to the limited therapeutic window of narrow therapeutic index (NTI) medications, cautious dosing and close monitoring are typically necessary. Although there are no generally accepted lists of NTI-drugs in the literature, NTI-drugs are generally defined as medications with a slight variation in plasma concentration range that causes both toxicity and efficacy. Cyclosporin, carbamazepine, digoxin, flecainide, lithium, phenytoin, phenobarbital, rifampicin, theophylline, warfarin, vancomycin, heparin, and other medications were all classified as NTI-drugs (11).

These are some of the drugs with their mechanism of action and pharmacokinetics:

PHENYTOIN (anti-convulsant):

Phenytoin's ability to bind to mammalian voltage-dependent sodium channels in neuronal cell membranes and extend their inactivation, particularly the rapid inactivated state, is largely responsible for its antiepileptic activity at therapeutic dosages. One important aspect of controlling seizures is preventing excessive neuronal activity, which is aided by this action (12).

CARBAMAZEPINE (anti-convulsant):

Carbamazepine (CBZ) primarily targets voltage-dependent sodium channels. The frequency of prolonged repeated action potential firing in cultured mammalian central neurons is reduced by CBZ and its metabolite, carbamazepine-epoxide. High-frequency firing is specifically inhibited by CBZ, whereas low-frequency firing is barely affected (13).

HEPARIN (anticoagulant):

Heparin increases its inhibition of thrombin and factor Xa by binding to antithrombin III (ATIII), which improves anticoagulation. Furthermore, heparin binds to thrombin directly, changing its structure and encouraging ATIII to inactivate thrombin. This two-way process has a strong anticoagulant effect (14).

VANCOMYCIN (antibiotic):

When UDP-MurNAc-pentapeptide is utilized as the substrate, vancomycin prevents the synthesis of peptidoglycans in *Gaffkya homari* membrane preparations; however, this is not the case when UDP-MurNAc-tetrapeptide or UDP-MurNAc-tripeptide are utilized. Perkins and Nieto's research on the complex formation between vancomycin and the peptide component is in line with this selectivity. The findings imply that neither complex formation with a cell wall acceptor nor the enzymes in charge of peptidoglycan production is involved in vancomycin's inhibitory activity (15).

WARFARIN (Oral anticoagulant):

Vitamin K and its epoxide form undergo cyclic conversion, which is disrupted by oral anticoagulants. The carboxylation of glutamate residues to γ -carboxyglutamate on vitamin K-dependent proteins is facilitated by vitamin K. Coagulation is inhibited by this interference because it decreases the activation of these proteins (16).

CLINICAL CHALLENGES AND RISKS

DOSE DEPENDENT ADVERSE EFFECTS AND TOXICITY

The term "adverse drug reaction" refers to a highly unpleasant or harmful reaction brought on by the use of a medication that suggests a possible risk from continued use and necessitates protective measures, specialized treatment, dosage modifications, or product

cessation. At the moment, these reactions are recorded using the WHO's Adverse Reaction Terminology, which will eventually be included in the International Classification of Diseases (17). "Adverse effect" is a better term than "toxic effect" or "side effect." An overreaction to the intended therapeutic effect is known as a toxic effect, and it usually happens at higher-than-normal dosages and is uncommon at regular levels (18).

Drug effectiveness typically has a distinct dose-response curve and is dose-dependent. Weight gain, Parkinsonism, hyperprolactinemia, and neurocognitive impairment are examples of adverse effects that are usually dose-related. There may be some dose-dependency in other affects as well, like diabetes, akathisia, and sexual dysfunction. It is yet unknown, nevertheless, if mortality rises in a dose-dependent fashion (19).

IMPLICATIONS OF SMALL DOSE (MICRO DOSE) OR PLASMA CONCENTRATION CHANGES

Low plasma-drug concentrations are an inevitable consequence of the low dose given in a human microdose research. Usually, it is used to evaluate the pharmacokinetics at higher therapeutic dosages (20).

A growing number of medications that have been documented in the literature with comparisons between their pharmacokinetics at a therapeutic dose and microdose. When a drug's effectiveness depends on its concentration in a particular type of cell or tissue, microdosing is used (21). Important characteristics of a microdosing unit include dosing stability, accuracy, precision, and flexibility. A patient's mortality may result from malfunctioning, which can have serious repercussions (22).

It improves adherence to treatment and patient comfort. It permits more delivery system downsizing by providing accurate dosage with highly concentrated drugs. Targeting previously unattainable tissues, this creates opportunities for novel medication delivery techniques (23).

PATIENT SPECIFIC FACTORS AFFECTING DRUG METABOLISM

Drug metabolism differs depending on age and tissue, with notable shifts occurring throughout the first few months of life. Due to different patterns of drug-metabolizing enzyme development, medication metabolism varies between adults and children. The effectiveness and safety of treatment are impacted by individual differences in drug metabolism, which are also influenced by genetic variants. Therapy can be optimized and adverse responses can be decreased by having a thorough understanding of metabolic pathways, implicated enzymes, and drug interactions (24). Due to their high drug use, co-morbidity, and age-related alterations in pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics, older adults are more likely to experience adverse drug responses (25). Alcohol has an impact on how many medications are metabolized and can lead to adverse drug reactions. Combining alcohol with several medications can result in a number of adverse drug reactions (ADRs), including headaches, nausea, vomiting, sleepiness, fainting, lack of coordination, hypotension, and many more (26). Additionally, smoking alters liver enzymes, which is a strong inducer of the hepatic cytochrome P-450, which impacts the metabolic process (27). Since numerous diseases coexist and various medications are used, people with multiple disorders are more susceptible to adverse drug reactions (ADRs) (28).

THERAPEUTIC DRUG MONITORING

Therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) is commonly understood to be the clinical laboratory measurement of a chemical parameter that will directly affect drug prescribing practices when properly interpreted by a physician. Otherwise, TDM refers to the process of customizing medicine dosage by keeping blood or plasma drug concentrations within a specific therapeutic window or range (29).

ROLE OF TDM IN OPTIMIZING NTI DRUG DOSING

A drug's pharmacokinetic behaviour and pharmacodynamic properties must be taken into account while determining the proper dosage schedules. This aids in evaluating the effects and behaviour of the drug in the body. Accurate dosage decisions depend on both aspects (30).

By preventing resistance from low serum exposure, TDM can enhance prognosis when there are fewer than five viable medications available. When high blood levels are detected, dosage changes can be made, which lowers adverse events and increases patient adherence (31).

TDM is crucial for figuring out the right dosages for people with hepatic or renal impairment because it concentrates on both pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics. To achieve the best possible treatment benefits with the least amount of toxicity, the

patient's blood profile is essential. Clinical management of immunosuppressive treatments, antiepileptic, anticancer, antibacterial, cardiac glycosides, and antitubercular drugs depends on TDM. With the growing usage of experimental medications and improved clinical pharmacology procedures, TDM's reach in India is anticipated to expand (32).

TECHNIQUES FOR MEASURING PLASMA DRUG CONCENTRATION

Total drug concentration is insufficient for therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) unless protein binding is minimal or the unbound portion remains constant. Additionally, protein binding and free concentration of drug influences drug ADME qualities via affecting pharmacokinetics (PK) and pharmacodynamics (PD) (33).

Consequently, drug-protein binding in PK investigations of a novel drug and the drug's free concentration in customized therapy are highly valuable. For this, a variety of methods have been employed, including calorimetry, spectroscopy, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), capillary electrophoresis (CE), equilibrium dialysis (ED), ultrafiltration (UF), and ultracentrifugation (UC). These techniques have been the subject of some reviews in recent years (34).

DRUG -DRUG INTERACTIONS AND DRUG FOOD INTERACTIONS

DRUG -DRUG INTERACTIONS

Drug-related problems (DRPs) can be prevented by closely monitoring a narrow therapeutic drug interactions were the most frequent (61%), with 241 DRPs among 120 patients taking NTIDs in this nine-month study carried out at a tertiary care hospital. The prevalence of DRP was significantly predicted by gender, comorbidities, polypharmacy, and extended hospital stays. The results highlight the vital role clinical pharmacists play in reducing DRPs and improving patient safety (35).

According to research 200 hospitalized patients, ages 18 to 95 (mean age: 47.75 years), were examined in the study (67% men, 33% females). The most prevalent illnesses were diabetes and hypertension, while the majority (56%) had no co-morbidities. 60% of patients received 5–10 medications out of a total of 5–22 prescriptions (average: 9.8). 18 adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and 108 medication interactions (33% avoidable) were found during the 6.7-day average hospital stay. Digoxin and phenytoin were among the NTI medications associated with increased drug-related issues (risk ratio 0.22 vs. 0.08, $p < 0.01$) (36).

In contrast to Norway's outpatient care rate of 3%, a survey revealed that 35% of hospitalized patients received prescriptions for NTI medications. Drug-related problems (DRPs) were more common with NTI medications, especially non-optimal dose, interactions, and monitoring requirements. Multivariate research demonstrated that NTI drug use is an independent predictor of DRPs, highlighting the importance of close observation in medical facilities (2).

INVOLVEMENT OF CYTOCHROME P450 ENZYME IN METABOLISM

Cytochrome P450 (P450) enzymes help xenobiotics oxidize, turning them into stable metabolites as well as chemically reactive intermediates. If the final product's reactivity is noticeably high, it may attach to one or more of the enzyme's catalytic sites, deactivating it. P450 enzyme inactivation during pharmacological therapy may result in serious drug interactions because the irreversible binding allows for sustained enzyme inhibition even after the offending medication has been removed from the body. This inhibition may have harmful effects by influencing the metabolism of medications having limited therapeutic windows, such as astemizole and terfenadine (37).

The clinical effects of CYP induction or inhibition vary, and if the victim drug has a narrow therapeutic index, this could be especially important because DDIs based on metabolism can alter the drug's concentration by up to ten times depending on whether biotransformation is induced or inhibited. The liver-resident CYP450 enzymes aid in the initial phase of the biotransformation of xenobiotic compounds. The liver is where drug metabolism mostly takes place, and the CYP1, CYP2, and CYP3 families are mostly responsible for this. The body's largest concentration of CYP450 enzymes is found in the liver (38).

Drug metabolism relies heavily on hepatic cytochrome P450 enzymes, which are the main route involved. Numerous isoforms of the CYP450 superfamily are capable of metabolizing a broad range of substrates. Clinically, inhibitions of these enzymes are important because they can affect the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of pharmaceuticals, especially when patients are administered many medications (polypharmacy) (39).

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS OF ALTERED DRUG METABOLISM AND ABSORPTION

Not all regulatory agencies have set standards for identifying narrow therapeutic index (NTI) pharmaceuticals, and there isn't a single, widely accepted list of NTI medications. According to European Medicines Agency (EMA) standards, decisions on the classification of NTI drugs must be decided on an individual basis while taking clinical aspects into consideration. A set of precise criteria cannot be developed. Similar to this, the FDA does not provide a complete list; nevertheless, product-specific guidelines can be used to identify NTI drugs that require stricter bioequivalence standards. Among the well-known NTI medications that must meet these more stringent bioequivalence standards are digoxin, valproic acid, carbamazepine, everolimus, phenytoin, and warfarin (40).

Ancient antiepileptic medications (AEDs) have the ability to either inhibit (like valproic acid) or stimulate (like carbamazepine, phenobarbital, phenytoin, and primidone) the metabolism of other AEDs, resulting in a decrease or increase in their serum concentrations, respectively. The enzyme inhibitors included in some antidepressants, antipsychotics, and antibacterial treatments like macrolides or isoniazid can raise the serum levels of antiepileptic medications (AEDs). In contrast, these levels can be lowered by a number of methods, such as increased excretion, decreased absorption, or enzyme induction, which can happen with drugs including antacids, probenecid, cimetidine, and oral contraceptives (41).

PHARMACOGENOMICS AND PERSONALISED MEDICINE GENETIC VARIATIONS AFFECTING NTI DRUG RESPONSE

Pharmacogenomics aims to develop methodical strategies for improving medication therapy according to a patient's genetic composition, with the goal of maximizing effectiveness and reducing side effects for each individual. According to Edwards and Aronson (2000), any drug that produces a positive therapeutic response may also have unfavourable side effects. "Pharmacogenetic or pharmacogenomic traits" (PGx traits) are the aggregate term for the different pharmacological responses—therapeutic, unfavourable, and toxic—that are categorized as phenotypes or traits in genetics. Because so many variables affect the ultimate phenotypic outcomes, there is a considerable amount of heterogeneity in medication reactions. The genetic underpinnings of this variation in medication responsiveness have been clarified by recent genome-wide pharmacogenomic investigations (42).

Individual variations in drug reactions may be greatly influenced by structural variations in pharmacodynamic genes, maybe to a greater extent than is now understood. Because these genes may have significant impact sizes, including them into pharmacogenetic testing offers encouraging prospects. The targets of over 70% of medications that have received FDA approval show structural diversity, especially in the form of copy number variation. Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) group N, which deals with treatments for the nervous system, has a substantial over-representation of drugs that target genes with copy number changes ($P=3.75e-5$). The incidence of these drugs varied throughout ATC classification groups. Genomic structural changes were identified to alter the targets of a number of medications with a restricted therapeutic index. Through the analysis of drug consumption data and the frequency of these structural changes, we were able to identify possible candidates for pharmacogenetic testing and customized prescription regimens (43).

In contrast to CYP3A, the population's activity distribution of other cytochrome P450 enzymes shows a polymodal pattern, which causes people to be categorized as either extensive or poor metabolizers. The existence of variable alleles and genetic polymorphisms have an impact on this variation. Different racial and ethnic groups have varying prevalences of variant alleles and the proteins that go along with them. But for a given patient, the crucial element is the particular enzyme genotype rather than the race or ethnicity, which are frequently determined by arbitrary standards (44).

PRECISION MEDICINE

Precision dosing, also known as customized dosage, modifies medication regimen according to patient characteristics (e.g., organ function, genetics), illness status, pharmacokinetics, and narrow therapeutic index (NTI). With a narrow window between therapeutic and harmful effects, NTI medications necessitate cautious dosage and therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM). NTI drugs have a therapeutic index of ≤ 2 or ≤ 3 . Better drug safety and efficacy are guaranteed by customized dose (Pater, 2004; Bialer et al., 1998) (45).

Advancements in oncology-based precision medicine include Because of the hazardous nature of the medications and their limited therapeutic range, phase I clinical trials for novel drugs usually included patients who had already tried every conventional therapy option rather than healthy volunteers. Patients with different cancer kinds should increase their dosage to prevent missing any

unexpected antitumor effects in less frequent tumors. These non-randomized trials were intended to establish the recommended phase II dose, which was the highest dose judged safe for further evaluation, as well as the dosing schedule (46).

Easy access to biomarker data at home and in clinical settings is essential to the full potential of personalized therapy. Precision medicine may be advanced by biosensors that allow for real-time monitoring of medications, hormones, and other analytes. Although glucose monitoring has helped diabetics, biosensors for other analytes are still not widely used. Increased use could improve patient care, especially when it comes to tracking the course of a disease and precisely dosing NTI medications (e.g., warfarin, troponin, NT-proBNP) (47).

ROLE OF HEALTH CARE PROFESSIONALS INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH (Physicians, Pharmacists, Nurses)

Better patient outcomes result from a team effort between physicians, nurses, and pharmacists, especially when it comes to medication administration. A study conducted in Australia showed that nurses and pharmacy employees working together might successfully treat individuals with mental health issues. While pharmacists handled prescriptions, nurses handled medical records, referrals, and patient care. Treatment disparities are decreased and patient safety is improved when nurses and pharmacists communicate clearly (48).

NURSES CONTRIBUTION TO INTERPROFESSIONAL PHARMACEUTICAL CARE

In pharmaceutical care, nurses are essential because they provide front-line services for health promotion, prevention, and treatment. In addition to monitoring side effects and preventing drug-related problems, they aid in medication management. Their involvement improves patient care, according to WHO recommendations. Assuming these duties raises the standard of care provided overall (49). In interprofessional care teams, members collaborate to provide patient-centered care, with pharmacists contributing alongside others. Effective teamwork requires confidence and a cooperative approach from all members. Administrators set goals within a collaborative framework, and the action plan is evaluated after implementation. The transdisciplinary team, utilizing their expertise, works together to improve professionalism and patient outcomes (50).

IMPORTANCE OF REGULAR MONITORING AND PATIENT FOLLOW -UP

By conducting reviews, monitoring use, and giving pharmaceutical information, pharmacists improve patient care. By working together with other experts, they help patients with long-term illnesses achieve better results. The reduction of long-term illness consequences depends on medication adherence. Pharmacists assist physicians by giving patients advice on how to take and adhere to their medications (51).

Hospitalized patients, particularly those experiencing respiratory distress, should have their vital signs, such as heart rate and respiration rate, closely monitored. However, for patients who are not critically ill, it is frequently performed sporadically. Physicians can gain important insights into clinical state by ongoing monitoring of these indicators. For patients who are at danger of hemodynamic or respiratory decompensation, this is particularly crucial (52).

REGULATORY AND PHARMACOECONOMICS ASPECTS

REGULATORY ASPECTS FOR NTI DRUGS

The FDA ensures that NTI pharmaceuticals are therapeutically equivalent to the reference drug by enforcing more stringent quality and bioequivalence (BE) standards than those for conventional drugs. Research and suggestions from FDA advisory groups and conversations are included in this. Generally speaking, generic medications adhere to the same BE standards as innovators, with research substantiating formulation or post-approval adjustments. Given the intricacy of NTI drugs, NDA applicants should seek advice from the FDA (53).

AVAILABILITY OF GENERIC NTI DRUGS AND THEIR CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

In many nations, pharmacists are able to automatically replace reference and generic medications because doctors are only required to prescribe the active ingredient. It is possible to switch between different generic versions of the same medication by using automatic generic substitution. This technique is required in many European nations, including Sweden and Germany. These programs seek to increase the effectiveness of healthcare resources while lowering costs (54).

FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND RESEARCH

INNOVATIONS IN DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM TO REDUCE NTI RISKS

1. Maintaining exact drug levels within the therapeutic range is a major difficulty in NTI drug management. Variations in absorption rates caused by traditional oral dosing frequently cause variations in plasma concentrations. New developments in medication delivery systems provide encouraging ways to reduce these dangers (55).
2. One such breakthrough is the controlled-release formulation, which helps maintain stable plasma concentrations by releasing the active ingredient gradually over time, minimizing the possibility of medication peaks and troughs that could result in toxicity or less than ideal therapeutic benefits (56).
3. The study of targeted drug delivery is crucial because it aims to improve the efficacy of medications by delivering them to particular tissues or organs while minimizing adverse effects across the body. This strategy reduces the variability related to the absorption of NTI medications in the body and permits more regulated dosage, which is particularly advantageous for these medications (57).

ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DOSING AND MONITORING

1. To enhance patient outcomes and decision-making, artificial intelligence (AI) is being used more and more in the healthcare industry. AI can be extremely helpful when it comes to NTI medications in terms of monitoring, forecasting, and optimizing dosage (58).
2. To improve individualized care, machine learning algorithms can analyse massive patient data sets, such as genetic information, comorbidities, and real-time medication levels, to forecast the best dosage for a given person (59).
3. They are also developing methods to model AI-driven estimates of NTI medication concentrations. AI systems are capable of forecasting possible shifts in plasma levels by considering several patient-specific factors, such as age, renal function, and available drugs. Because of this, doctors can adjust dosages proactively and prevent harmful plasma concentrations (60).

NEED FOR FURTHER RESEARCH ON UNDEREXPLORED NTI DRUGS

1. Many NTI medications are still not fully understood in the literature, despite the fact that the dangers of well-known NTI medications like warfarin, digoxin, and lithium are widely known (61).
2. These medications may be less well-studied in extensive clinical trials since they are more recent or are used to treat specialized medical disorders. Research in this field must be expanded in order to completely comprehend the pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and clinical hazards of these medications (62).
3. More investigation is specifically required into new NTI medications that may result from the creation of new treatments. New NTI medications are probably going to be developed as biotechnology develops, particularly in areas like gene therapy and oncology where accurate drug targeting and dosage are crucial (63).

All title and author details must be in single-column format and must be centered. Every word in a title must be capitalized. Email address is compulsory for the corresponding author.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, NTI drugs pose significant challenges in clinical practice due to their narrow therapeutic range and increased potential for adverse effects. Proper dosing and continuous monitoring are essential to ensure effectiveness while minimizing the risk of toxicity. Factors like individual patient conditions, drug interactions, and variations in metabolism need careful consideration when managing these medications. Vulnerable populations, such as the elderly, require particular attention and tailored treatment. Therapeutic Drug Monitoring (TDM) plays a crucial role in maintaining safe and precise dosing. Additionally, advances in pharmacogenomics and personalized medicine offer valuable approaches to enhancing NTI drug therapy. Precision dosing, supported by biomarkers and AI, allows for more individualized treatment strategies. Collaboration among healthcare providers is vital for improving patient outcomes. Strengthening regulatory guidelines and exploring new drug delivery technologies are key to managing NTI drug risks effectively. Ongoing research into both existing and new NTI drugs will continue to refine treatment methods. Ultimately, these combined efforts aim to improve patient safety, increase therapeutic efficacy, and minimize side effects, leading to more effective management of NTI medications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Not Applicable.

REFERENCES

1. Sam Habet, Narrow Therapeutic Index drugs: clinical pharmacology perspective, *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, Volume 73, Issue 10, October 2021, Pages 1285–1291, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpp/rgab102>
2. [Mark Donnelly](#), [Lanyan Fang](#), [Rajanikanth Madabushi](#). Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs: FDA Experience, Views, and Operations. 11 November 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpt.3460>.
3. Burns, M. Management of Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs. *J Thromb Thrombolysis* 7, 137–143 (1999). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008829403320>
4. Sam Habet. Narrow Therapeutic Index (NTI) Drugs: Definitions and Criteria. *Authorea*. January 04, 2023. [10.22541/au.167285903.32760018/v1](https://doi.org/10.22541/au.167285903.32760018/v1)
5. McKenzie LE, Kimberlin, CL, Pendergrast JF, Berado, DH. Potential drug interventions in a highrisk ambulatory elderly population. *J Geriatr Drug Ther* 1994;8:137:49–63.
6. Pivdiro AS. Managing medication in the elderly. *Hosp Direct* 1995;59–64
7. PhD Leslie M. Shaw, PhD David W. Holt, MD Paul Keown et.al. Current opinions on therapeutic drug monitoring of immunosuppressive drugs. Accepted 16 August 1999, Available online 27 January 2000. DOI : [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2918\(99\)80044-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2918(99)80044-7)
8. Bryan A. Liang MD, PhD, JD, Tim K. Mackey MAS, Kimberly M. Lovett MD. Illegal “No Prescription” Internet Access to Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs. Accepted 28 March 2013, Available online 15 April 2013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinthera.2013.03.019>
9. Tamargo, J., Le Heuzey, JY. & Mabo, P. Narrow therapeutic index drugs: a clinical pharmacological consideration to fentanyl. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol* 71, 549–567 (2015). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00228-015-1832-0>
10. Muller, P., Milton, M. The determination and interpretation of the therapeutic index in drug development. *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 11, 751–761 (2012). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd3801>
11. Blix HS, Viktil KK, Moger TA, Reikvam A. Drugs with narrow therapeutic index as indicators in the risk management of hospitalised patients. *Pharm Pract (Granada)*. 2010 Jan;8(1):50-5. doi: 10.4321/s1886-36552010000100006. Epub 2010 Mar 15. PMID: 25152793; PMCID: PMC4140577.
12. [Mervyn J. Eadie](#). Phenytoin. First published: 02 October 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118936979.ch43>
13. Ambrósio, A.F., Soares-da-Silva, P., Carvalho, C.M. et al. Mechanisms of Action of Carbamazepine and Its Derivatives, Oxcarbazepine, BIA 2-093, and BIA 2-024. *Neurochem Res* 27, 121–130 (2002). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014814924965>
14. Raymund Machovich. Mechanism of action of heparin through thrombin on blood coagulation. [Volume 412, Issue 1](#), 18 November 1975. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-2795\(75\)90334-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-2795(75)90334-7)
15. Hammes WP, Neuhaus FC. 1974. On the Mechanism of Action of Vancomycin: Inhibition of Peptidoglycan Synthesis in *Gaffkya homari*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.6.6.722>
16. Jack Hirsh, MD, FCCP · James E. Dalen, MD, FCCP · Daniel Deykin et.al. Oral Anticoagulants Mechanism of Action, Clinical Effectiveness, and Optimal Therapeutic Range. [Volume 108, Issue 4, Supplement 231S-246S](#) October 1995. DOI: [10.1378/chest.108.4_Supplement.231S](https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.108.4_Supplement.231S)
17. [Prof I Ralph Edwards, FRCP](#), [Jeffrey K Aronson, FRCP](#). Adverse drug reactions: definitions, diagnosis, and management. Published October 7, 2000. DOI: [10.1016/S0140-6736\(00\)02799-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(00)02799-9)
18. Stephens MDB. Definitions and classifications of adverse reaction terms. In: Stephens MDB, Talbot JCC, Routledge PA, eds. The detection of new adverse reactions, 4th edn. London: Macmillan Reference, 1998: 32–44.
19. Kazunari Yoshida, Hiroyoshi Takeuchi. Dose-dependent effects of antipsychotics on efficacy and adverse effects in schizophrenia. 20 January 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbr.2020.113098>
20. Lappin, G., Noveck, R., & Burt, T. (2013). Microdosing and drug development: past, present and future. *Expert Opinion on Drug Metabolism & Toxicology*, 9(7), 817–834. <https://doi.org/10.1517/17425255.2013.786042>

21. Lappin, G. (2010). Microdosing: Current and The Future. *Bioanalysis*, 2(3), 509–517. <https://doi.org/10.4155/bio.09.177>
22. A.I. Geller, N. Shehab, M.C. Lovegrove et.al. National estimates of insulin-related hypoglycemia and errors leading to emergency department visits and hospitalizations *JAMA Intern. Med.*, 174 (2014), pp. 678-686, [10.1001/jamainternmed.2014.136](https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2014.136)
23. Agnes Beate Bußmann , Lorenz Maximilian Grünerbel , Claudia Patricia Durasiewicz et.al. Microdosing for drug delivery application—A review. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sna.2021.112820>
24. [Stefanie D. Krämer](#), [Bernard Testa](#). The Biochemistry of Drug Metabolism – An Introduction. First published: 19 October 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbdv.200900233>
25. Wynne H. Drug metabolism and ageing. *British Menopause Society Journal*. 2005;11(2):51-56. doi:10.1258/136218005775544589
26. Muae Jamal Alomar. Factors affecting the development of adverse drug reactions. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsps.2013.02.003>
27. Tomlinson JEM, McMahon AD, Chaudhuri R, et al. Efficacy of low and high dose inhaled corticosteroid in smokers versus non-smokers with mild asthma *Thorax* 2005;**60**:282-287.
28. [Noriko Daneshtalab BSc](#), [Dr Richard Z. Lewanczuk MD](#) et.al. Rheumatoid Arthritis Does Not Reduce the Pharmacodynamic Response to Valsartan. First published: 08 March 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091270003262951>
29. Kang JS, Lee MH. Overview of therapeutic drug monitoring. *Korean J Intern Med*. 2009 Mar;**24**(1):1-10. doi: 10.3904/kjim.2009.24.1.1. PMID: 19270474; PMCID: PMC2687654.
30. [Sebastian G. Wicha](#), [Anne-Grete Mårtson](#), [Elisabet I. Nielsen](#), [Birgit C.P. Koch](#), [Lena E. Friberg](#) et.al. From Therapeutic Drug Monitoring to Model-Informed Precision Dosing for Antibiotics. 10 February 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpt.2202>
31. Giovanni Sotgiu, Jan-Willem C. Alffenaar et.al. Therapeutic drug monitoring: how to improve drug dosage and patient safety in tuberculosis treatment. 23 March 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2014.12.001>
32. Dipesh Prajapati. Optimizing Patient Care: A Review on Therapeutic Drug Monitoring of some Clinically used Drugs. [Vol. 3 No. 04 \(2023\): International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Clinical Research](#). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22377/ijpscr.v3i04.175>
33. W.W. Mapleson. Computation of the effect of Donnan equilibrium on pH in equilibrium dialysis. [Journal of Pharmacological Methods Volume 17, Issue 3, May 1987, Pages 231-242](#). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-5402\(87\)90053-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-5402(87)90053-2)
34. Behrouz Seyfinejad, Sibel A. Ozkan, Abolghasem Jouyban. Recent advances in the determination of unbound concentration and plasma protein binding of drugs: Analytical methods. [Talanta Volume 225](#), 1 April 2021, 122052. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2020.122052>
35. Charmi Manoj Chhatrala, Bhanu Kumar M and Nikita Pal. Assessment of drug-related problems associated with narrow therapeutic index drugs: A prospective cohort study July 28, 2023 <https://doi.org/10.1177/25160435231190192>
36. Kapil Iyer^{1*}, Neha Dilipkumar¹, Sharmin Vasaya¹, Sunita Pawar, Arundhati Diwan. Comparison of Drug Related Problems Associated with Use of Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs and Other Drugs In Hospitalized Patients 2018; 10(3): 318-321
37. Yasuhiro Masubuchi & Toshiharu Horie. Toxicological Significance of Mechanism Based Inactivation of Cytochrome P450 Enzymes by Drugs 10 Oct 2008 <https://doi.org/10.1080/1040844070121523>
38. Srinivas Maddi^{1*}, Thirumaleswara Goud² and Pratima Srivastava¹. Cytochrome P450 Enzymes, Drug Transporters and their Role in Pharmacokinetic Drug-Drug Interactions of Xenobiotics: A Comprehensive Review 11 July, 2017 DOI: 10.17352/ojc.000006
39. Yuan Wei¹ & Chenxiao Tang¹ & Vinayak Sant¹ & Song Li¹ & Samuel M. Poloyac¹ & Wen Xie¹. A Molecular Aspect in the Regulation of Drug Metabolism: Does PXR-Induced Enzyme Expression Always Lead to Functional Changes in Drug Metabolism 4 May 2016 DOI 10.1007/s40495-016-0062-1
40. Lucia Gozzo^{1,2}, ORCID, Filippo Caraci^{3,4,5} and Filippo. Drago Bioequivalence, Drugs with Narrow Therapeutic Index and the Phenomenon of Biocreep: A Critical Analysis of the System for Generic Substitution 26 July 2022 <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10081392>

41. Svein I. Johannessen and Cecilie Johannessen Landmark. Antiepileptic Drug Interactions – Principles and Clinical Implications 01 Sep 2010 <https://doi.org/10.2174/157015910792246254>
42. Ge Zhang a, Daniel W. Nebert. Personalized medicine: Genetic risk prediction of drug response 14 February 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2017.02.036>
43. Rasmussen, Henrik Berg; Dahmcke, Christina Mackeprang. Genome-wide identification of structural variants in genes encoding drug targets Possible implications for individualized drug therapy July 2012. DOI:10.1097/FPC.0b013e328352c770
44. Grant R. Wilkinson. Drug Metabolism and Variability among Patients in Drug Response May 26, 2005 DOI: 10.1056
45. Rachel J. Tyson Rachel J. Tyson | Christine C. Park Christine C. Park | J. Robert Powell J. Robert Powell | Precision Dosing Priority Criteria: Drug, Disease, and Patient Population Variables 22 April 2020 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2020.00420>
46. Pauline du Rusquec^{1,2}, Thomas Filleron³, Christophe Le Tourneau. Drug development in the era of precision medicine in oncology—Clues beyond randomization June 06, 2021 doi: 10.21037/cco-21-29
47. Watkins, Zachary. Beyond Glucose: Breakthroughs in Translating Electrochemical Aptamer Biosensors into Point-of-care and Wearable Platforms for Longitudinal Monitoring of Clinically Relevant Analytes August 03, 2025 <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4789-1846>
48. Waszyk-Nowaczyk M, Guzenda W, Dragun P, Olsztyńska L, Liwarska J, Michalak M, et al. Interdisciplinary Cooperation between Pharmacists and Nurses—Experiences and Expectations. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health [Internet]. 2022 Sep 16;19(18):11713.
49. Dilles T, Heczkova J, Tziaferi S, Helgesen AK, Grøndahl VA, Van Rompaey B, et al. Nurses and Pharmaceutical Care: Interprofessional, Evidence-Based Working to Improve Patient Care and Outcomes. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health [Internet]. 2021 Jun 2;18(11):5973.
50. Ahlam juwaybir Alanazi¹, Fahad hassan saeed alqahtani, Ahmed Nasser Altamimi et.al. The role of pharmacists, nurses, and medical practitioner in medication adherence and personalized medicine. DOI: 10.53555/jptcp.v29i04.5080
51. Presley B, Groot W, Pavlova M. Pharmacists' and patients' perceptions about the importance of pharmacist services types to improve medication adherence among patients with diabetes in Indonesia. BMC Health Services Research. 2021 Nov 13;21(1).
52. [Eyal Zimlichman](#), [Martine Szyper-Kravitz](#), [Avraham Unterman](#) et.al. How is my patient doing? Evaluating hospitalized patients using continuous vital signs monitoring. Isr Med Assoc J. 2009 Jun;11(6):382-4. PMID: 19697594
53. De Baetselier E, Dilles T, Batalha LM, Dijkstra NE, Fernandes MI, Filov I, et al. Perspectives of nurses' role in interprofessional pharmaceutical care across 14 European countries: A qualitative study in pharmacists, physicians and nurses. Schneider CR, editor. PLOS ONE. 2021 May 27;16(5):e0251982.
54. [Lucia Gozzo](#), [Filippo Caraci](#), [Filippo Drago](#). Bioequivalence, Drugs with Narrow Therapeutic Index and the Phenomenon of Biocreep: A Critical Analysis of the System for Generic Substitution. 2022 Jul 26;10(8):1392. doi: [10.3390/healthcare10081392](https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10081392)
55. Burns M. Management of narrow therapeutic index drugs. Journal of Thrombosis and Thrombolysis. 1999;7(2):137–43.
56. Habet S. Narrow Therapeutic Index drugs: clinical pharmacology perspective. Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology. 2021 Aug 4;73(10).
57. Jiang W. FDA Drug Topics: Understanding Generic Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/media/162779/download>
58. Dr. Ramesh Roshan Yadav, Dr. Yogananda R, B. Shankar Reddy. Narrow therapeutic index drugs-a critical study on prescription trends in south Indian tertiary care hospital. 03 Nov. 2018 DOI: 10.20959/wjpr201819-13691
59. Hege S, Blix, Kirsten K, Viktil, Tron A, Moger, and Aasmund Reikvam. Drugs with narrow therapeutic index as indicators in the risk management of hospitalised patients. Pharm Pract (Granada). 2010 Jan-Mar; 8(1): 50–55. Published online 2010 Mar 15. doi: 10.4321/s1886-36552010000100006
60. DrugBank. Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs | DrugBank Online [Internet]. go.drugbank.com. Available from: <https://go.drugbank.com/categories/DBCAT003972>

61. Physicochemical failure modes for Narrow Therapeutic Index (NTI) drugs [Internet]. European Pharmaceutical Review. 2021 [cited 2025 Jan 27]. Available from:
<https://www.europeanpharmaceuticalreview.com/article/157918/physicochemical-failure-modes-for-first-line-therapy-narrow-therapeutic-index-nti-drugs-a-call-for-attention-nti-risk-classification-and-new-prior-knowledge/>
62. Gentry EP. Empirical evidence of risk penalties for NTI Drugs. Journal of Risk and Uncertainty [Internet]. 2019;58(2/3):219–44.
63. Texas NDP PharmD Clinical Assistant Professor Director, Austin/San Antonio Area Community Pharmacy Residency Program. The University of Texas at Austin College of Pharmacy Austin. Generic Substitution of Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs [Internet]. www.uspharmacist.com. [cited 2023 Mar 10].

Cite this Article: Ahamed, S.K., Laxmi, R.V., Kumar A.R., Kumar, M.N., Chakala, V., Tadikond, R.R. (2025). Clinical Insights into Narrow Therapeutic Index Drugs. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(3), pp. 1106-1116. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i3-13>